

Strength Perception in Swami Vivekananda's Philosophy of Education

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ABSTRACT : The present study highlights on Swami Vivekananda's idea of strength and how this message has been transmitted into three domains, viz religion, socio-political and educational ambit. Swami Vivekananda taught us that strength or fearlessness is a combined perception of psycho-physical, social, moral and spiritual acumen which is an internal-construct. Vivekananda like the Aeschylean hero, dreamt to build a magnificent narrative of modern India by spreading the fire of liberty, equality and fraternity among men and women and in doing so, education is the one and only method. Vivekananda developed his concept of man making to build strength of character which lies dormant deep within our soul.

Keywords : Courage, Optimism, Education, Religion

*If the sun by the cloud is hidden a bit,
If the welkin shows but gloom,
Still hold on yet a while, brave heart,
The victory is sure to come.*

– Swami Vivekananda : Hold on yet a while,
brave heart

Vivekananda being a doyen of Enlightenment has always energized the coming generation to widen their outlook and experience through the message of strength and courage. He believed

that strength, fearlessness and freedom are the three cardinal qualities of human being and physical freedom, mental freedom, and spiritual freedom are watchwords of growth and development. When we are talking about 'freedom' in its physical, psychological and spiritual dimensions, it represents the concept of a knowledge structure. The two elementary qualities, we know, of any knowledge structure are the ability to differentiate and the ability to integrate and Vivekananda's idea of freedom is best reflected when he says, "what is the object

of the Jnana-yoga? Freedom. Freedom from what? Freedom from our imperfections.....” (New discoveries. 3.358.2) He himself believed that it is freedom that gives us mastery over all nature and it is impossible without knowledge. Thus Vivekananda’s concept of freedom, courage, fearlessness has a cognitive structure of its own and man is pure and free at all times to change the nature and is capable to determine his own life by his own actions. So Vivekananda’s dream-culture is about the total man, strong in biceps and determined in original thinking, not over-eager ‘to have’ but more ‘to be’.

Vivekananda’s ‘The lectures from Colombo to Almora’ is the Gita of the 21st century and many more centuries to come which is meant to rouse millions of Tamasic Arjunas to be courageous for hard work and puissant vigour. So, Vivekananda’s gospel of strength is summarized in the following remarks: “I know that truth alone gives life, and nothing but going towards reality will make us strong and none will reach truth until he is strong strength is the medicine which the poor must have when tyrannized over by the rich, nothing gives such strength as the idea of Monism. Nothing makes us so moral as the idea of Monism”. (c.w of Sw. Vivekananda Vol.II.P.201).

Strength is the medicine that the ignorant must have when oppressed by the learned. Let us try to concentrate on Vivekananda’s idea of strength and how it has been formulated in the three different domains, viz, religious, socio-political and educational. Vivekananda taught us that strength or valour is a combined perception of physical, mental, moral and spiritual acumen which is an internal-construct.

Vivekananda was primarily a religious preacher, an ascetic, a philosophical idealist, but was simultaneously a pragmatist which is expressed in his various statements that India’s socio-political slavery from time immemorial is rooted in the suppression of the poor masses. As a result, the age-old tyranny and suppression had snatched the individuality of these dead-like people living in unspeakable poverty. For any rejuvenation of the country, it was extremely necessary to take positive and constructive steps for raising the masses up, so that they were to be saved from the four evils of i) priest craft, ii) poverty, iii) tyranny, and iv) ignorance. Vivekananda realized like a prophet that in this journey towards enlightenment, there are two weapons to combat with: one is the education and the other is the religion which are nothing but the two sides of the same coin. If education is the manifestation of perfection already in man’, then ‘religion is the manifestation of divinity already in man’ Vivekananda himself has drawn our attention in this respect: “*Bring all light into the world. Light, bring light! Let light come unto every one; the task will not be finished till everyone has reached the Lord. Bring light to the poor; and bring more light to the rich, for they require it more than the poor. Bring light to the ignorant, and more light to the educated, for the vanities of the education of our time are tremendous! Thus bring light to all and leave the rest unto the Lord, for in the words of the same Lord, ‘To work you have the right and not to the fruits thereof’. ‘let not your work produce results for you, and at the same time may you never be without work’.* (c.w. Vol.III.P.247) Thus Vivekananda’s philosophy of work is an expression of his idea of strength and courage. The clarion call- Arise, awake and stop not till

the goal is reached, uttered by the greatest Vedantic teacher of modern times at the Parliament of religions in Chicago over 124 years ago is still reverberating on the ever-perrinial sky of optimism being the be-all and end-all solution for all the maladies the world is still facing at present. *“Vivekananda's gospel is that of energism, of mastery over the world, over the conditions surrounding life, of human freedom, of individual liberty, of courage trampling down cowardice, of world-conquest. And those who are acquainted with the trends of the world thought since the middle of the nineteenth century, are aware of the fact that it was just along these lines that the West was groping in the dark to find a solution. The most formidable exponent of these wants and shortcomings- was the German man of letters and critic, Nietzsche, his famous writing Als Sprach Zorathustra (1885) and other works have awakened mankind to the need of a more positive human and joyous life's philosophy than that of the New Testament. This joy of life for which the religious, philosophical and social thought was anxiously waiting came suddenly from an unexpected quarter, from the unknown young man of India. And Vivekananda was acclaimed as the pioneer of a revolution – the positive and constructive counterpart to the destructive criticism of Nietzsche”.* (Sarkar, 1936). The key-note of Vivekananda's man-making and character building education stands on his strength- giving religion. He reminded us not to be afraid because the history of humanity has only acknowledged the courageous. Fear is the cause of all sufferings and it is fearlessness that brings heaven down the earth. Vivekananda told us that religion is to be verified through the

test of logic. His outstanding legacy was that he infused life and religion. To him: strength is religion. *“The essence of my religion is strength. The religion that does not infuse strength into the heart, is no religion to me, be it of the Upanishads, the Gita or the Bhagvatam. Strength is greater than religion and nothing is greater than strength”.* (c.w. Vol.II, p.699). Vivekananda only preached the Upanishads and according to him, of the Upanishads, it is only that One idea, strength. *“The quintessence of the Vedas and Vedanta and all lies in that one word, Buddha's teaching was non-resistance, or non-injury For behind that non-injury lay a dreadful weakness. It is weakness that conceives the idea of resistance”.* (c.w. Vol VIII, p.267). Vivekananda was not in the scheme of resistance as Buddha had expressed. Strength or fearlessness was his only concern. To Vivekananda, religion is the manifestation of the natural strength inherent in man. A spring of infinite valour is coiled up inside this little body. *“This is the history of man, of religion, civilization, or progress. That giant Prometheus, who is bound, is getting himself unbound. It is always a manifestation of strength.....”* (c.w. Vol VIII. p.185). Vivekananda like the Aeschylean hero, dreamt to create a new world by distributing the fire of liberty, equality and fraternity among men and women. He believed that religion is not confined only within do and don't; religion is not something external or an exhibition of lifeless intellectualism. The same echoing spirit of Macmurry, (1961:157) while discussing about relational philosophy of religion is worthy to be mentioned here. *“Religion must be concerned with the original and basic formal problem of human existence, and this is the relation of persons.*

Since religion is a reflective activity, this must mean..... that religion has its ground and origin in the problematic of the the relation of persons, and reflects that problem. In this case religion is about the community of persons”.

The basic philosophy of Vivekananda stands on the two maxims – ‘Being’ and ‘Making’. If the first one is an internal construct, then the second one is an external construct. Both the constructs deserve a psycho-social as well as cognitive constructivist space. He developed his concept of man-making to build strength of character which is the key to Vivekananda’s philosophy. Vivekananda asserted: *”Being of one mind is the secret of society. And the more you go on fighting and quarrelling about all trivialities such as ‘Dravidian’ and ‘Aryan’, and the question of Brahmins and non-Brahmins and all that, the further you are off from that accumulation of energy and power which is going to make the future India”* (c.w. Vol.III P.299). Vivekananda realized that “the root of all misery in India is the wide gulf between the lower and upper classes. Unless this difference is made up, there is no hope of any well-being for the people (1957, p.137). Vivekananda dreamt of removing this social inequality through the process of ‘levelling up’ not through ‘levelling down’, not through the taking down of the upper classes, but through the lifting up of the lower classes and it is possible only through education. Vivekananda was ready to refuse his personal desire for deliverance for the sake of mass upliftment. “Who cares for your *bhakti* and *mukti*? I will go to hell cheerfully a thousand times, if I can rouse my countrymen, immersed in Tamas, and make them stand on their own feet”.(1981.p.252)

Vivekananda vehemently protested against the west-imitative new generation of India as well as always backward- looking blind orthodoxy. “There are two great obstacles on our path in India, the scylla of old orthodoxy and the charybdis of modern European civilization” (c.w. Vol. III.p.151). He himself has offered the best solution of these horns of adilemma.”Stand and die in your own strength; if there is any sin in the world, it is weakness; avoid all weakness, for weakness is sin, weakness is death” (ibid. P. 151). This is the key message of Vivekananda from where his philosophy of man-making is roused; this is the basic concept from where the three major future oriented temporal perspectives in positive psychology – self-efficacy, optimism, and hope – have come into existence. Bandura (1997) defined self-efficacy as “*peoples’ beliefs in their own actions*”. We may define ‘hope’ as goal-directed thinking in which the person utilizes simultaneously his ability to find routes to desired goals and the perceived motivation to use those routes. Let us have a look on what Vivekananda has asserted:”We should cultivate the optimistic temperament, and endeavour to see the good that dwells in everything”. (c.w. Vol. IV. P.190) Vivekananda is an immortal icon who always invigorates us by his shower of optimism, “If a bad time comes, what of that? The pendulum must swing back to the other side” (c.w. Vol. VIII. p.280) He, as it were reminds us, “nothing is wasted, nothing is in vain./ The seas roll over but the rocks remain.” (Herbert, A.P. (1890-1971): Tough at the top (operetta c.1949). Vivekananda has encouraged us that we need not worship any gods in the world if we have faith, strength, love and these will accompany us all throughout hard time.

Vivekananda believed that the most potent weapon in the hands of the oppressor is the mind of the oppressed. So the mind has to be changed and in this solemn expedition, education is the only panacea. We want that education by which character is formed, strength of mind is increased, the intellect is expanded". (c.w. Vol. V. 342) Vivekananda developed his concept of man-making to build strength of character which lies dormant deep within our soul. "..... strength must come to the nation through education". (c.w. Vol. VIII, p. 267). Burning faith, strong will-power, resolute determination are the vast reservoir of strength. Vivekananda was the living apostle of manliness who equated religion with strength, socio-political regeneration with strength, educational revitalization with strength. His is an education which is a reveille and which teaches a lesson for all life – face the terrible, face it boldly. Vivekananda said to his disciple Sarat Chandra Chakravarty: "If you can think that infinite power, infinite knowledge and indomitable energy lie within you, and if you can bring out that power, you also can become like me go and preach to all, 'Arise, awake, sleep no more; within each of you there is the power to remove all wants and all miseries. Believe this, and that power will be manifested.'" (c.w. Vol. VI P. 454). Vivekananda's mission of life was to instill the principles of strength that stimulate all-round development. He spent all his energy to awaken our hidden potentialities by reminding us not only of our divine heritage, but also to think that unless an energy comes from across the seas, it will not be possible to shake off the lethargy of the nation of Lotus-eaters, to rouse their dormant spirit, and that the medium of the Occident is necessary to infuse life and vigor into our fossilised constitution. His

'man-making religion', 'man-making education' are vital to human development. Man-making in the sense of developmental raising of the human being from self to self is the central thrust of his philosophy. Vivekananda wanted to make our civilisation vigorous and fearless, using physical, intellectual, and spiritual strength. True education can never be achieved by the weak-*navamatmabalahinenalabhyah*. "The true man", according to Vivekananda, "is he who is strong as strength itself and yet possesses a woman's heart. You must feel for the millions of beings around you, and yet you must be strong and inflexible"(c.w. Vol. III. P.448) Vivekananda wanted man-making religion, man-making theories, man-making education. Education is a search for integration, for wholeness. It must include the development of man's spiritual powers. Education must help to build a harmonious, self-confident personality. Vivekananda tried earnestly to lift the veil of ignorance from the mind of man by giving a spiritual orientation to education. Spirituality, we have taught from Vivekananda, is one's inner strength that makes one transcends the barriers of worldliness. Spirituality, we know, helps one realize one's connection with truth. Vivekananda's concept of religion, socio-politics and education – all are stemmed from the same source that tells about the fulfillment of man's life, an experience in which "every aspect of his being is raised to its highest extent. What is needed is a change of consciousness, a rebirth, an inner evolution, a change in understanding" through the process of education. Vivekananda was splendidly rhetorical in his vision of new India with most impassioned philanthropic outburst: "let her arise – out of the peasants' cottage, grasping the plough; out of the huts of the fishermen, the cobbler, and the

sweeper. Let her spring from the grocer's shop, from beside the oven of the fritter-seller. Let her emanate from the factory, from marts, and from markets these common people..... have suffered eternal misery, which has given them unflinching vitality. Living on a handful of grain, they can convulse the world..... And besides they have got the wonderful strength that comes of a pure and moral life, which is not to be found anywhere else in the world" (c.w. Vol. VIII, 327) There are very few Indian or western educationists who have such an altruistic moorings with the dispossessed. The concept of strength occupies a central place in Vivekananda's philosophy of education. Vivekananda's message of strength has two unique features : (a) Firstly, according to Vivekananda, "Strength, strength it is that we want so much in this life, for what we call sin and sorrow have all one cause, and that is our weakness" (c.w. Vol. I. 381.2) secondly, according to Vivekananda, "All power is within you. Believe in that; do not believe that you are weak.... stand up and express the Divinity within you" (c.w. Vol. III.284). Vivekananda is not the name of a person; he is the perfect expression of India's soul, the ever- inspiring source of eternal optimism. To conclude we may quote the following lines:

No coward soul is mine,

No trembler in the world's storm-troubled sphere;

I see Heaven's glories shine,

And faith shines equal, arming me from fear.

[Emily Bronte (1818-48) : 'No coward soul is mine' (1846)]

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